

Semantic Modelling of Intermedial and Intertextual References in Comics: A Case Study on Max Baitinger's *Sibylla* (2021)

Oberreither, Bernhard

bernhard.oberreither@oeaw.ac.at
Austrian Academy of Sciences, Österreich
ORCID: 0000-0001-8609-2433

Untner, Laura

laura.untner@fu-berlin.de
Freie Universität Berlin, Deutschland
ORCID: 0000-0002-9649-0870

Serles, Katharina

serles@mdw.ac.at
University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna,
Österreich
ORCID: 0000-0003-3476-8002

Abstract

This paper explores the epistemic potentials and methodological limitations of semantic modelling for representing complex intermedial and intertextual phenomena in literary artifacts, specifically, comics. Being the result of an interdisciplinary collaboration, the paper engages in a dialogue between close reading, formal modelling, and the utilisation of knowledge graphs for DH research. Using an analysis of the comic *Sibylla* (2021) by Max Baitinger as a case study, it aims to assess the degree to which semantic web technologies can constitute a framework for in-depth representation of ‘traditional’ humanities’ knowledge on literary and visual references while doing so in a structured and interoperable way. Can the promises of semantic modelling – transparency, computability, and epistemic rigor – be meaningfully fulfilled in a task of this complexity?

Introduction: Semantic Modelling and the Humanities

Digital Humanities scholarship has not only identified data modelling as one of its core activities with intrinsically

epistemic and interpretive value (e.g. Flanders and Jannidis, 2019; Ciula et al., 2023), it has also increasingly turned to Linked Data as a promising framework for the formal representation of humanistic knowledge (cf. Golub et al., 2021; Antopolosky, 2022; Nurmiko-Fuller, 2024). Within literary studies, this development is mirrored by a number of emerging Linked Data projects, yet only a few of these explicitly tackle the semantic modelling of intertextual – and even less so intermedial – relationships (e.g. Horstmann et al., 2023; Hinzmann et al., 2024; Pianzola et al., 2024).

Unlike traditional databases or informal annotation systems, Linked Data systems often rely on ontologies – formal, shared, and explicit specifications of conceptualizations – that claim to offer a transparent and theoretically grounded modelling of domain knowledge. Together with authority identifiers, they allow for interoperability across projects and disciplines. As Fabio Ciotti (2014) and others have emphasized, the methodological advantage of ontologies for the humanities lies in their capacity to formalize and explicate what often remains implicit in humanistic analysis: the theoretical assumptions underpinning scholarly work.

How can such formal systems, designed for machine-readability and computational reasoning, adequately represent the nuanced, context-sensitive, and often ambivalent concepts used in literary studies? What is gained – and what is potentially lost – when scholarly insights into intertextuality and intermediality are transformed into structured, machine-readable data? These questions become particularly pressing when the subject of analysis is itself a highly reflexive, multilayered, and intermedially complex artifact such as Max Baitinger's *Sibylla* (2021), a comic that engages in a multifaceted dialogue with literary history and gendered authorship.

The Case Study: Max Baitinger's *Sibylla* (2021)

This case study examines the comic *Sibylla* to evaluate the strengths and limitations of semantic modelling in representing intermedial and intertextual references. Central to this inquiry is the question: To what extent can an RDF data model – specifically one based on the INTRO ontology – accommodate the needs of both interpretive literary analysis and computationally tractable knowledge representation?

The comics medium is inherently hybrid, intermedial, and self-/meta-referential (Sina, 2016; Serles, 2018) and as such particularly well-suited for discussing referentiality, intermediality, and intertextuality. Due to its constituent repetitions, the medium forms a reference system in itself, achieving coherence by recreating its objects across panels (Etter and Rippl, 2013). At the same time, it fundamentally destabilizes reference by producing what Ole Frahm describes as “repetitions without an original,” thereby problematizing

referentiality in a fundamentally parodic way (2010, 33 and 37; our trans.).

It is within this complex medial framework that *Sibylla* becomes a compelling object of analysis: Published in 2021 and awarded with the Berthold Leibinger Stiftung comic book prize, Baitinger's work engages deeply with the literary and cultural legacy of the German baroque poet Sibylla Schwarz (1621–1638). It interweaves historical, biographical, and literary narratives, addressing Schwarz's life during the Thirty Years' War, her reception across centuries, the construction of her authorial personae, and the ways in which her work has been mythologized and categorized.

What makes *Sibylla* interesting for this study is the way it creates a dense web of references that traverse not only temporal and cultural, but also medial and semiotic boundaries, constantly questioning (and parodying) its own mode of historical narration. The comic opens with a performative gesture – “Einen Strich in die Landschaft und behaupten ... // ... das hier sei jetzt Sibylla Schwarz:” (“Draw a line in the landscape and claim ... // ... that this is now Sibylla Schwarz,” 4f., our trans.) – as a black line enters the page and transforms into the stylized figure identified as Schwarz. The figure's reductive form, especially the flat blackness of her dress, continually recalls this initiating gesture of the black line. A subsequent self-referential sequence further destabilizes the possibility of historical authenticity and representation. Here, the comic reflects on its own production context (i.e. a collaboration with the Sibylla Schwarz Association on the occasion of her 400th birthday) and stages a quotation from the 1650 posthumous publication of Schwarz's complete works, edited by Samuel Gerlach. The quote, initially framed as Schwarz's voice, is later revealed to be Gerlach's. In response, the comic's version of Schwarz closes the book and throws it into the sea (a pointed visual metaphor for discarding a distorted and distorting reception).

This interrogation culminates in a René Magritte-inspired scene in which the narrator asserts that anyone who would believe the depicted figure was in fact “Sibylla Schwarz,” was “a fool” (our trans.; the joke draws on the pun that in German, Pfeife means both “pipe” and “fool”), visually referencing Magritte's famous painting *The Treachery of Images* (1929). The scene thus challenges and destabilizes the semiotic triangle and (historical) representation.

Later in the comic, this pipe reappears: the figure of Schwarz discovers it and puts it in her mouth while holding a pillow that displays an image of Sappho. This striking visual constellation, i.e. combining the pipe (a stand-in for unstable representation), the Schwarz figure, and a cultural image of Sappho, underlines the constructed nature of historical and poetic identity.

This analysis focuses on exactly this specific subset of *Sibylla*'s intertextual network, i.e. its references to the ancient Greek poet Sappho, who served as an important point of reference for Schwarz herself (Untner, 2023, 422). In Baitinger's comic, Sappho is evoked both explicitly and implicitly – through textual quotation and visual allusion, across verbal and iconographic layers (Stemmann, 2025) –

and, as this case study argues, even more frequently than in Schwarz' own work. This overemphasis corresponds with a long-standing reception history that exaggerates Schwarz's affinity with Sappho, effectively imposing a lineage onto her that the comic simultaneously stages and critiques.

Methodological Approach: Dual Perspectives

Sibylla provides a rich testing ground for assessing how semantic technologies can – or cannot – adequately model the multifaceted ways in which texts and images refer to, reframe, and recontextualize one another across media. This case study approaches its object in two complementary ways: a close reading informed by literary and comic studies, and a formal modelling approach grounded in DH and especially semantic methodologies.

Close Reading and Theoretical Framing

From the perspective of literary and comic studies, the analysis undertakes a close reading of *Sibylla* with particular attention to the mechanisms of intertextuality, intermediality, and interpictoriality. Drawing on theoretical frameworks from intermediality (e.g. Rajewsky, 2002; Wolf 2018) and comic studies (e.g. Bachmann et al., 2012; Packard et al. 2019), the study shows how visual and textual references of different kinds, such as quotes, allusions, and mentions, operate in tandem to produce, and sometimes undermine, meaning across panels and pages. The analysis is also attentive to the medium-specific phenomenon of problematizing referentiality, where the relationship between signifier and signified is deliberately unsettled (Frahm, 2010) – a feature that will prove to be challenging to formalize.

Semantic Modelling and Linked Data

The study also draws on an existing project dedicated to tracing the German-language literary reception of Sappho (Untner, 2024–[2027]). This project approaches literary reception as an intertextual phenomenon, aiming for comprehensive machine-readable documentation and classification. The core of its infrastructure is a semantic data model based heavily on the CIDOC CRM aligned INTRO ontology for the representation of intertextual, intermedial, and interpictorial relationships (Oberreither, 2019ff.). Using this ontology and its ability to not only model interrelations, but also the textual and pictorial features they are based on (e.g. Oberreither, 2023, 2024), this study models the references found in *Sibylla*, focussing on the relations between Sibylla Schwarz and Sappho as well as their works. The modelling process involves identifying and classifying different types of relations and finding structured representations that can be computationally queried and analyzed.

Theoretical and Practical Challenges

The core research question – how well semantic modelling meets the needs of both interpretive and computational perspectives – requires a critical assessment of several interrelated challenges:

Granularity

One of the most pressing challenges is that of granularity. Literary analysis frequently focuses on a research object in great detail, and thus demands fine-grained access to its features or parts on different levels. This applies all the more to a comic's distinct structural and semantic units and their segmenting and referencing functions. In the case of *Sibylla*, intertextual and intermedial relations operate on multiple levels of image, text, and respective features. This necessitates a modelling approach that is not only precise, but also flexible enough to accommodate varying degrees and types of interrelation. To what degree can a formal ontology built for standardization and formalization accommodate these specific demands – and do so without the data becoming unwieldy and ultimately uncomputable?

Specificity

A related challenge is that of specificity. Humanities scholarship often relies on context-sensitive and object-specific terminologies which are long rooted in theoretical discourse and frequently adapted to the peculiarities of a given work, especially when dealing with a comparably young research object such as comics. Ontologies, by contrast, require generalizable categories and stable definitions. How can these two modes of knowledge representation – specific and general – be brought into constructive alignment? The modelling approach taken in this case study tests whether the INTRO ontology is sufficiently extensible to incorporate concepts derived from comics theory, including medium-specific notions such as the aforementioned parodistic subversion of referentiality.

Computability

Finally, this study addresses the issue of computability. Fundamentally, the aim is to reconcile the two poles of conceptual modelling, the 'modelling-of' (the data model's representation of the object domain) and the 'modelling-for' (the model's functionality for further processing; McCarty, 2008). Even if intertextual and intermedial phenomena can be modeled to a degree satisfying literary and comic scholars to provide a well-documented formalized representation of the research result, is the resulting graph actually useful for substantive digital analysis? Can it be

meaningfully queried or compared – or does its complexity render it effectively opaque to computation? Also: What are the epistemological implications of the balancing act aimed for? Questions like these become especially important when dealing with literary features (like references) that are ambiguous or multivalent – features that are key to the openness and complexity that define literary meaning.

Interdisciplinary Collaboration

This case study is the product of an interdisciplinary project team:

- a Digital Humanities researcher with expertise in semantic web technologies and data modelling and a research focus on Sappho's literary reception history,
- a literary and comics scholar specializing in intertextuality, gender, visual narrative, and the baroque, with no DH background,
- and a Digital Humanities and literary scholar with a background in literary theory and methodology who created the INTRO ontology.

The collaboration is structured as an iterative process including joint sessions of modelling, theoretical discussion, and re-modelling, starting out with an analysis of the intertextual and intermedial references in *Sibylla* – to be formalized and modelled by the DH part of the team. Interim results are evaluated by all three participants with regard to applicability in their respective fields.

Interim Results and Further Challenges

Interim results include first illustrative modellings created for further evaluation and re-modelling, to be expanded later with additional test modellings. Three of the modellings created thus far and presented below focus on one specific panel and the comic scholar's interpretations connected to it: On page 32 (s. Figure 1), Schwarz uses a cushion that shows the face of Sappho as a mask. This can be read as references not only to Sappho's person and oeuvre, but also to discourse on Sappho since she is present in the form of 'merchandise', pointing to a tradition of collectively constructing and commodifying the author's persona. At the same time, this hints at the discourse on Schwarz and the construction of the Schwarz persona, which the comic reflects in great depth.

Figure 1: The page with the respective insert panel from Baiteinger's *Sibylla*, 32.

1) A generalized modelling of interrelations between an artistic expression and other expressions or corpora (s. Figure 2) provides a simple and easily computable structure. Specificity can be added by classifying intermedial relations based on domain-specific taxonomies, or by choosing a subclass for the interrelation specifying the media involved (e.g. intertextual, inter pictorial, intermedial). In implementing a taxonomy via *INT11 Type of Interrelation*, the issue of specificity can be addressed at this level already.

Figure 2: A generalized modelling.

2) A high-granularity modelling (s. Figure 3) can, for example, put the focus on a specific passage (the image area in question) where the character Sibylla Schwarz covers her face with the cushion. Granularity is provided on the one

hand by separating the expression from its parts (the image area), and by separating them from their contents (the features they actualize). All of these statements are modelled in the same modular fashion, thereby keeping the complexity of, for example, SPARQL queries to a minimum.

Figure 3: A more granular modelling.

3) While the second modelling adds granularity and specificity, it falls short in one important respect: It fails to communicate how the panel's different aspects of meaning build on each other in a layered manner. The third modelling (s. Figure 4) resolves this issue by chaining modules through their actualizations of features: This corresponds to the sequence of statements (and possibly the sequence of interpretation steps) that together form the scholarly reading of the panel. At the same time, the still homogeneous structure of the modules does not necessarily impair handling (i.e. creation and querying) of the data set.

Figure 4: A modular modelling.

Outlook

Data modelling can be understood as a “process of signification” that entails constant “translation and negotiation of meaning” (Ciula et al., 2023, 67). The proposed study is ideally suited to illustrate just that: In a collaborative setting, it investigates the complexities of modelling scholarly knowledge on literature, its transferability to the digital medium, and the challenges and implications that come with it. This way, it contributes to the discussion of the mutual convergence of digital and ‘traditional’ methods, and to the ongoing exploration of the role of semantic technologies in the humanities.

Bibliography

- Antopolsky, Alexander B.** 2022. “Linked Open Data in the Digital Humanities (Review of Publications).” *Scientific and Technical Information Processing* 49 (2): 119–126.
- Bachmann, Christian A., Véronique Sina, and Lars Banhold, eds.** 2012. *Comics intermedial*. Essen: Bachmann.
- Baitinger, Max.** 2021. *Sibylla*. Berlin: Reprodukt.
- Ciotti, Fabio.** 2014. “Digital Literary and Cultural Studies: State of the Art and Perspectives.” *Between* 8 (4). <https://doi.org/10.13125/2039-6597/1392> (last accessed: 25 July 2025).
- Ciula, Arianna, Øyvind Eide, Cristina Marras, and Patrick Sahle.** 2023. *Modelling Between Digital and Humanities. Thinking in Practice*. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers.
- Etter, Lukas, and Gabriele Rippl.** 2013. “‘Don’t laugh – this ain’t the funny pages’: Comics und bildende Kunst (Alain Séchas, Raymond Pettibon).” In *Interpiktorialität. Theorie und Geschichte der Bild-Bild-Bezüge*, ed. by Guido Isekenmeier, 261–278. Bielefeld: Transcript.
- Flanders, Julia, and Fotis Jannidis, eds.** 2019. *The Shape of Data in the Digital Humanities. Modeling Texts and Text-based Resources*. London: Routledge.
- Frahm, Ole.** 2010. *Die Sprache des Comics*. Hamburg: Philo Fine Arts.
- Golub, Koraljka, Ahmad M. Kamal, and Johan Vekselius.** 2021. “Knowledge organisation for digital humanities.” In *Information and Knowledge Organisation in Digital Humanities. Global Perspectives*, ed. by Koraljka Golub and Ying-Hsang Liu, 1–22. London: Routledge.
- Hinzmann, Maria, Matthias Bremm, Tinghui Duan, Anne Klee, Johanna Konstanciak, Julia Röttgermann, Moritz Steffes, Christof Schöch, and Joëlle Weis.** 2024 [Preprint]. “Patterns in modeling and querying a knowledge graph for literary history.” In *Pattern Theory in Language and Communication*, ed. by Sabine Arndt-Lappe, Milena Belosevic, Peter Maurer, Claudine Moulin, Achim Rettinger, and Sören Stumpf. Trier: TCLC. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13991180> (last accessed: 21 November 2025).
- Horstmann, Jan, Christian Lück, and Immanuel Normann.** 2023. “Systems of Intertextuality. Towards a formalization of text relations for manual annotation and automated reasoning.” In *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 17 (3). <http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/17/3/000731/000731.html> (last accessed: 21 November 2025).
- Ilgner, Julia.** 2022. “Alte(rnde) Autoren. Biofiktionale Gerontopoetik im zeitgenössischen Dichterroman.” In *Alter & Ego. (Auto)fiktionale Altersfigurationen in deutschsprachiger und nordischer Literatur*, ed. by Jutta Schloon, Thorsten Pöplow, Maike Schmidt, Julia Ilgner, and Michael Grote, 84–107. München: Iudicium.
- McCarty, Willard.** 2008. “Knowing ... : Modeling in Literary Studies.” In *A Companion to Digital Literary Studies*, ed. by Ray Siemens and Susan Schreibman. Oxford: Blackwell. <https://companions.digitalhumanities.org/DLS> (last accessed: 25 July 2025).
- Nurmikko-Fuller, Terhi.** 2024. *Linked Data for Digital Humanities*. London: Routledge.
- Oberreither, Bernhard.** 2019ff. *INTRO – the intertextual, inter pictorial, and intermedial relations ontology*. <https://github.com/BOberreither/INTRO> (last accessed: 25 July 2025).
- Oberreither, Bernhard.** 2023. “A Linked Data Vocabulary for Intertextuality in Literary Studies, with some Considerations Regarding Digital Editions.” In *Digitale Edition in Österreich | Digital Scholarly Edition in Austria*, ed. by Roman Bleier and Helmut W. Klug, 69–87. Norderstedt: Books on Demand.
- Oberreither, Bernhard.** 2024. “Text and Image Are the Same, or Close Enough at Least. Reflections on Expanding an Ontology for Intertextual Relations Towards Intermediality.” Presentation at *Linked Open Data and Literary Studies*, Nov. 19–Nov. 20, 2024, Berlin. https://www.temporal-communities.de/research/digital-communities/resources/lod-resources/Bernhard_Oberreither_Text_and_Image.pdf (last accessed: 25 July 2025).
- Packard, Stephan, Andreas Rauscher, Véronique Sina, Jan-Noël Thon, Lukas R.A. Wilde, and Janina Wildfeuer.** 2019. *Comicanalyse. Eine Einführung*. Stuttgart: J. B. Metzler.
- Pianzola, Federico, Franziska Pannach, Luotong Cheng, L., Xiaoyan Yang, and Luca Scotti.** 2024. *GOLEM Ontology for Narrative and Fiction*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14911392> (last accessed: 21 November 2025).
- Rajewsky, Irina O.** 2002. *Intermedialität*. Tübingen: Francke.
- Serles, Katharina.** 2018. “BILDER SEHEN ERZÄHLEN. Kunstbetrachtung im Comic.” *closure. Kieler e-journal für Comicforschung* 4.5, 134–146. <http://www.closure.uni-kiel.de/closure4.5/serles> (last accessed: 25 July 2025).

Sina, Véronique. 2016. *Comic – Film – Gender. Zur (Re-)Medialisierung von Geschlecht im Comicfilm.* Bielefeld: Transcript.

Stemmann, Anna (2025). “Fast wäre sie poetisch ausfällig geworden.” Max Baitingers Comic *Sibylla* (2021).” In S. Bremerich, M. Heuß, M. Wiegandt (Eds.), *Form-Gewinn. Abhandlungen zur Literaturwissenschaft* (pp. 257–270). J. B. Metzler. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-70981-8_20 (last accessed: 21 November 2025).

Untner, Laura, ed. 2023. *Sappho. Texte zur literarischen Rezeption im deutschsprachigen Raum.* Würzburg: Königshausen & Neumann.

Untner, Laura. 2024–[2027]. *Sappho digital. Die literarische Sappho-Rezeption im deutschsprachigen Raum.* <https://sappho-digital.com> (last accessed: 25 July 2025).

Wolf, Werner. 2018. “Intermedialität: Konzept, literaturwissenschaftliche Relevanz, Typologie intermedialer Formen [2014].” In *Selected Essays on Intermediality by Werner Wolf (1992–2014). Theory and Typology, Literature-Music Relations, Transmedial Narratology, Miscellaneous Transmedial Phenomena*, ed. by Walter Bernhardt, 173–210. Leiden and Boston: Brill/Rodopi.